

Volumetric and ultrasonic studies of diglycine in binary aqueous solutions of saccharide at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K

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Abstract : Densities, speeds of sound and viscosities of diglycine have been measured at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K in aqueous saccharides solutions ranging from 1.0 to 5.0 mass% of saccharide. The saccharides used are mannose, maltose and raffinose. From density, viscosity and speed of sound data, apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} , relative viscosity η_r and adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ of diglycine have been determined. The viscosity data have been analysed using the Jones-Dole equation. Partial molar volumes V_{ϕ}^0 and partial molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}^0$ of diglycine at infinite dilution were evaluated. These values are required for calculating hydration number n_H of diglycine. Transfer volumes ΔV_{ϕ}^0 , and transfer adiabatic compressibilities ΔK_{ϕ}^0 from water to aqueous saccharide solutions have been calculated. The results have been discussed in terms of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions and the structural changes of the solutes in solutions.

Keywords : Apparent molar volume, adiabatic compressibility, viscosity, diglycine, aqueous saccharide solutions.

Introduction

The amino acids are the building units of other complex biomolecules such as antibiotics and proteins. Therefore, study of thermodynamic properties of amino acids can provide valuable information about conformational stability and interactions of larger biomolecules in solutions. In recent years, there has been considerable interest in the determination of various thermodynamic properties of amino acids, small peptides and their derivatives¹⁻⁸. These properties play an important role in the study of various processes in proteins like denaturation, dissociation into subunits and the activity of enzymes.

As direct study of these important protein-water or protein-water-additive interactions is difficult because of the complexity of the interactions in such a large biomolecules^{9,10}. Therefore, for a better understanding of the hydration behavior of proteins, one useful approach is to study simpler model compounds such as amino acids.

A variety of thermodynamic properties, such as enthalpy of dissolution^{11,12}, enthalpy of dilution^{15,16}, partial molar heat capacity^{17,18}, partial molar volume^{7,17-21}, viscosity²⁰ and adiabatic compressibility^{22,23} have been determined for aqueous solutions of amino acids. Invest-

tigations of systems containing amino acids in presence of aqueous mixed solvents have also aroused much attention^{11,21,24-26} recently. So it can be helpful to study interaction of various amino acids and peptides, which form good model for proteins, in water and aqueous solutions of various additives in order to understand the mechanism of denaturation and stabilization of proteins by these agents. In fact, there are extensive studies on volumetric and thermochemical properties studies of amino acids in aqueous solutions^{18,19}, but very few in aqueous saccharide solutions²⁷⁻²⁹. In our previous work³⁰, thermodynamic studies of some amino acids + monosaccharides + water system have been carried out by using volumetric, transport and acoustic measurements.

Here we report the apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ}^0 and apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ of diglycine in binary aqueous solutions of mannose, maltose and raffinose (1-5 mass%) obtained from experimentally measured density and speed of sound data. From these data, the partial molar volumes V_{ϕ}^0 , partial molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}^0$ and the partial molar expansibilities ϕ_E^0 at infinite dilution have been obtained. These are used to calculate the transfer parameters ΔV_{ϕ}^0

and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ and hydration number n_H of amino acid. The viscosity data have been utilized to compute values of viscosity B -coefficients, free energy of activation. Such data are expected to highlight the role of amino acid in presence of aqueous saccharide solution and its influence with temperature.

Results and discussion

The densities and speeds of sound at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K for solutions of diglycine in binary aqueous solutions of saccharide (mass percentage of saccharide = 1, 3 and 5) are given in Table 1, while Table 2 shows the values of density and viscosity of diglycine at different mass percentage and at the measured temperatures.

The apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} and apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ were calculated from the solution density and the sound speed results with the following equations :

$$V_{\phi} = M/\rho + 1000 (\rho_0 - \rho)/m\rho\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

$$K_{\phi,s} = M \beta_s/\rho + (1000/m\rho\rho_0) (\beta_s\rho_0 - \beta_{s,0} \rho) \quad (2)$$

where M is the relative molar mass of the solute (kg mol^{-1}), m is the molality (mol kg^{-1}) of the solution, and ρ_0 , ρ , $\beta_{s,0}$ and β_s are the densities (kg m^{-3}) and coefficient of adiabatic compressibilities (Pa^{-1}) of pure solvent and solution, respectively. The resulting values of apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} , adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ and the molal concentrations m of diglycine in different concentration of saccharides at various temperatures are also included in Table 1.

The measured speeds of sound u have been combined with densities ρ in order to calculate adiabatic compressibility coefficient according to the Laplace equation,

$$\beta_s = 1/(u^2\rho) \quad (3)$$

where u is the speed of sound and ρ is the density of the solution.

The variation of apparent molar quantities with molality can be adequately represented by the relation :

$$Y_{\phi} = Y_{\phi}^0 + S_Q m \quad (4)$$

where Y_{ϕ}^0 (Y_{ϕ}^0 denotes V_{ϕ}^0 or $K_{\phi,s}^0$) is the limiting value of the apparent partial molar property (equal to partial molar property at infinite dilution) and S_Q (S_Q denotes S_V or S_K) is the experimental or limiting slope. The slope S_Q

of eq. (4) is usually very small. Eq. (4) was fitted to our experimental V_{ϕ} and $K_{\phi,s}$ values in different saccharide solutions by the method of least squares to evaluate the partial molar volume V_{ϕ}^0 and adiabatic compressibility $K_{\phi,s}^0$ at infinite dilution.

The values of V_{ϕ}^0 , $K_{\phi,s}^0$, S_V and S_K for diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions at temperatures 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K are given in Table 3 along with the standard errors. The experimental values of V_{ϕ}^0 and $K_{\phi,s}^0$ for diglycine in water at three temperatures are reported in the foot note of Table 3.

The types of interactions occurring between the peptide molecules and saccharide molecules can be classified as follows :

- (i) Hydrophilic-ionic interactions between the -OH group of the saccharides and the zwitterionic centers of the peptide.
- (ii) Hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions between the nonpolar side groups of the saccharide molecules and the peptide.
- (iii) Hydrophilic-hydrophilic interactions between the -OH group of the saccharide molecules and the -OH group of the peptide.
- (iv) Hydrophilic-hydrophobic interactions between the -OH group of the saccharide molecules and the nonpolar side group of the peptide.

The perusal of Table 3 shows that the amino acid studied here has positive V_{ϕ}^0 and negative $K_{\phi,s}^0$ in aqueous saccharide solutions at different temperatures thereby showing the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. The increase in V_{ϕ}^0 values for diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions may be attributed to the increase in solvation of diglycine at higher temperature as well as at higher region of saccharides, i.e. cosolute saccharide-solvent interactions increase on increasing mass% of saccharide in solutions.

It is evident from Table 3 that the values of S_V are more negative at higher mass% of maltose at the measured temperatures, suggesting the presence of weak ion-ion interaction. It may be said that the solvation of ion decreases with the increase of mass% of maltose in solutions.

The partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) and partial molar adiabatic compressibilities of transfer ($\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$)

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	288.15 K			298.15 K			308.15 K					
	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	μ (m s ⁻¹)	$V_{\phi} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$K_{\phi,s} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	μ (m s ⁻¹)	$V_{\phi} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$K_{\phi,s} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	μ (m s ⁻¹)	$V_{\phi} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$K_{\phi,s} \times$ 10^6 (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)
					Diglycine + 1% mannose							
0.0000	1.002952	1470.36	-	-	1.000827	1500.45	-	-	0.997745	1523.03	-	-
0.0526	1.005989	1474.57	74.10	-42.20	1.003810	1504.55	75.16	-37.72	1.000681	1526.95	76.12	-33.62
0.0819	1.007658	1477.19	74.25	-44.01	1.005448	1506.95	75.33	-38.28	1.002297	1529.19	76.23	-33.80
0.1005	1.008710	1479.33	74.37	-47.44	1.006476	1508.78	75.46	-40.14	1.003310	1530.90	76.36	-35.36
0.1263	1.010155	1481.26	74.49	-45.35	1.007891	1510.61	75.63	-38.46	1.004709	1532.64	76.49	-33.92
0.1487	1.011404	1484.56	74.59	-50.83	1.009115	1512.83	75.73	-39.90	1.005907	1534.70	76.65	-35.04
0.1841	1.013353	1486.21	7479	-46.64	1.011024	1515.27	75.93	-37.99	1.007780	1537.00	76.88	-33.26
0.2002	1.014231	1487.70	74.88	-40.80	1.011880	1516.64	76.05	-38.04	1.008624	1538.29	76.99	-33.31
					Diglycine + 3% mannose							
0.0000	1.010238	1477.60	-	-	1.008003	1506.99	-	-	1.004876	1528.95	-	-
0.0599	1.013633	1482.24	74.99	-37.41	1.011346	1511.39	75.89	-34.48	1.008164	1533.16	76.87	-29.29
0.0841	1.014989	1484.23	75.07	-38.75	1.012675	1513.31	76.04	-31.95	1.009478	1534.94	76.93	-29.29
0.1013	1.015938	1486.03	75.22	-40.76	1.013606	1514.91	76.21	-33.77	1.010392	1536.91	77.13	-31.32
0.1257	1.017282	1487.88	75.34	-39.77	1.014927	1516.73	76.33	-34.46	1.011697	1538.21	77.22	-30.64
0.1606	1.019193	1491.04	75.47	-40.69	1.016797	1519.62	76.51	-34.09	1.013542	1540.92	77.37	-30.87
0.1809	1.020289	1492.67	75.58	-40.31	1.017877	1521.17	76.60	-33.90	1.014602	1542.44	77.48	-30.74
0.2166	1.022190	1494.21	75.81	-36.09	1.019747	1523.28	76.81	-31.96	1.016447	1545.13	77.68	-30.53
					Diglycine + 5% mannose							
0.0000	1.018880	1484.86	-	-	1.016542	1513.65	-	-	1.013303	1535.19	-	-
0.0208	1.020059	1486.90	74.98	-48.56	1.017697	1515.55	76.14	-41.30	1.014444	1536.39	76.87	-21.22
0.0604	1.022278	1490.25	75.22	-42.96	1.019894	1518.68	76.33	-36.76	1.016596	1539.92	77.04	-32.33
0.0986	1.024381	1494.32	75.52	-46.40	1.021937	1522.48	76.61	-39.55	1.018639	1543.41	77.27	-34.45
0.1425	1.026764	1497.72	75.78	-42.65	1.024277	1525.77	76.85	-36.70	1.020949	1546.62	77.54	-32.34
0.1806	1.028798	1500.16	76.03	-39.10	1.026274	1528.67	77.08	-35.33	1.022915	1549.73	77.80	-32.15
0.2048	1.030063	1502.83	76.23	-40.55	1.027518	1530.53	77.27	-34.68	1.024145	1551.14	77.99	-30.56

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2481	1.032323	1506.93	76.46	-40.84	1.029737	1534.30	77.49	-34.78	1.026329	1554.66	78.24	-30.53
0.0000	1.002800	1470.36	-	-	1.000676	1500.34	-	-	0.997617	1522.81	-	-
0.0441	1.005329	1474.24	74.53	-46.81	1.003157	1503.96	75.65	-39.78	1.000064	1526.21	76.49	-34.82
0.0898	1.007938	1477.83	74.47	-43.68	1.005716	1507.38	75.60	-37.48	1.002588	1529.50	76.43	-33.24
0.1085	1.009005	1479.25	74.41	-42.85	1.006764	1508.75	75.53	-36.94	1.003620	1530.86	76.38	-33.05
0.1205	1.009692	1481.05	74.36	-46.99	1.007434	1510.37	75.51	-40.24	1.004280	1532.26	76.36	-33.39
0.1661	1.012275	1484.25	74.31	-43.69	1.009973	1513.44	75.43	-37.59	1.006787	1535.29	76.26	-33.48
0.1759	1.012835	1485.20	74.27	-44.13	1.010517	1514.27	75.41	-37.75	1.007322	1536.12	76.25	-33.74
0.2146	1.015020	1488.70	74.22	-37.36	1.012663	1517.51	75.31	-38.12	1.009440	1539.09	76.17	-33.78
0.0000	1.010483	1475.75	-	-	1.008256	1505.27	-	-	1.005079	1527.44	-	-
0.0552	1.013540	1480.71	76.28	-44.57	1.011259	1509.90	77.29	-37.84	1.008060	1531.83	77.76	-33.72
0.0796	1.014889	1482.75	76.20	-43.37	1.012583	1511.86	77.23	-37.17	1.009374	1533.64	77.70	-32.78
0.0970	1.015853	1484.59	76.12	-45.26	1.013527	1513.53	77.17	-38.45	1.010312	1535.21	77.64	-33.98
0.1150	1.016847	1486.31	76.07	-45.63	1.014503	1515.13	77.12	-38.80	1.011282	1536.70	77.58	-34.20
0.1498	1.018753	1489.57	75.98	-45.72	1.016374	1518.12	77.03	-38.69	1.013302	1539.48	77.48	-34.90
0.1820	1.020545	1491.74	75.84	-43.13	1.018125	1520.33	76.94	-36.99	1.014881	1541.65	77.38	-32.80
0.1917	1.021101	1492.91	75.81	-44.19	1.018673	1521.29	76.90	-37.54	1.015399	1542.52	77.36	-33.10
0.0000	1.018011	1481.95	-	-	1.015692	1510.92	-	-	1.012468	1532.63	-	-
0.0496	1.020725	1486.37	76.77	-41.97	1.018353	1515.12	77.86	-36.33	1.015104	1536.56	78.44	-31.73
0.0852	1.022689	1490.27	76.44	-47.08	1.020277	1518.67	77.56	-39.94	1.017008	1539.88	78.15	-34.96
0.1031	1.023682	1491.52	76.28	-44.32	1.021358	1519.93	77.38	-38.88	1.017974	1541.12	77.97	-33.58
0.1197	1.024605	1492.92	76.13	-43.68	1.022150	1521.21	77.24	-37.26	1.018869	1542.35	77.83	-33.02
0.1478	1.026175	1496.20	75.87	-46.52	1.023693	1524.12	76.99	-39.23	1.020390	1544.91	77.59	-33.12
-0.1806	1.028023	1498.35	75.54	-43.40	1.025492	1526.24	76.73	-30.78	1.022173	1547.01	77.32	-32.18
0.1997	1.029086	1500.48	75.39	-44.54	1.026556	1528.21	76.52	-7.91	1.023220	1548.86	77.15	-33.34
0.0000	1.002500	1469.36	-	-	1.000393	1499.45	-	-	0.997335	1522.14	-	-
0.0611	1.006020	1474.73	74.20	-47.11	1.003843	1504.48	75.38	-40.20	1.000735	1526.88	76.26	-35.31

Table-1 (contd.)

0.0859	1.007430	1476.85	74.31	-46.44	1.005224	1506.56	75.50	-40.25	1.002097	1528.83	76.37	-35.29
0.0999	1.008215	1478.93	74.44	-55.57	1.005996	1508.35	75.60	-43.80	1.002859	1530.43	76.45	-38.04
0.1269	1.009730	1480.64	74.56	-47.05	1.007483	1510.00	75.70	-40.11	1.004326	1532.06	76.55	-35.15
0.1399	1.010452	1481.59	74.64	-46.01	1.008188	1510.91	75.80	-39.26	1.005023	1532.89	76.63	-34.29
0.1822	1.012792	1485.54	74.81	-46.47	1.010482	1514.58	75.91	-39.58	1.007286	1536.38	76.79	-34.73
0.1874	1.013075	1486.15	74.85	-46.89	1.010760	1515.14	75.97	-39.93	1.007558	1536.87	76.84	-34.92
Diglycine + 3% raffinose												
0.0000	1.009629	1474.62	-	-	1.007437	1504.28	-	-	1.004316	1526.54	-	-
0.0557	1.012801	1479.45	74.75	-44.27	1.010545	1508.80	75.93	-37.66	1.007380	1530.83	76.77	-33.32
0.0783	1.014069	1481.55	74.90	-45.12	1.011791	1510.74	76.02	-38.26	1.008608	1532.62	76.87	-33.51
0.1003	1.015295	1483.33	75.01	-43.89	1.012995	1512.51	76.12	-37.83	1.009796	1534.31	76.96	-33.26
0.1168	1.016209	1484.84	75.10	-44.13	1.013890	1513.86	76.22	-37.66	1.010680	1535.58	77.04	-33.10
0.1484	1.017945	1485.55	75.30	-43.61	1.015592	1516.42	76.38	-37.27	1.012361	1538.02	77.18	-32.85
0.1821	1.019770	1490.49	75.43	-43.27	1.017384	1519.12	76.53	-36.79	1.014127	1540.56	77.35	-32.37
0.1864	1.020007	1491.24	75.46	-44.46	1.017616	1519.50	76.56	-37.78	1.014356	1541.18	77.37	-33.20
Diglycine + 5% raffinose												
0.0000	1.017167	1480.80	-	-	1.014587	1509.95	-	-	1.011698	1531.44	-	-
0.0578	1.020353	1487.03	76.37	-41.10	1.018013	1515.91	77.43	-35.16	1.014778	1536.82	78.29	-30.43
0.0721	1.021132	1488.03	76.43	-48.96	1.018775	1516.60	77.52	-40.93	1.015533	1537.68	78.32	-32.82
0.0957	1.022406	1489.25	76.58	-41.66	1.020026	1517.82	77.65	-35.16	1.016765	1538.91	78.46	-31.05
0.1149	1.023435	1492.17	76.69	-47.72	1.021036	1520.26	77.75	-39.17	1.017763	1541.69	78.54	-32.23
0.1536	1.025497	1494.77	76.84	-42.72	1.023063	1522.83	77.87	-35.66	1.019764	1543.49	78.65	-30.92
0.1834	1.027062	1497.43	76.99	-42.42	1.024602	1525.36	78.00	-35.23	1.021285	1545.87	78.77	-30.85
0.2026	1.028058	1498.91	77.10	-41.35	1.025586	1526.93	78.08	-35.27	1.022254	1547.43	78.86	-30.86

Table 2. Densities (ρ) and viscosity (η) of diglycine in aqueous solutions of saccharides at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K

<i>m</i> (mol kg ⁻¹)	288.15 K		298.15 K		308.15 K	
	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPas)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPas)
Diglycine + 1% mannose						
0.0000	1.002952	1.1690	1.000827	0.9292	0.997745	0.7221
0.0571	1.006246	1.1951	1.004054	0.9488	1.029835	0.7720
0.0669	1.006976	1.2036	1.004605	0.9549	1.035371	0.7808
0.0760	1.007323	1.2074	1.005116	0.9593	1.040483	0.7870
0.1508	1.011519	1.2622	1.009231	0.9962	1.082433	0.8377
0.1600	1.012028	1.2693	1.009723	1.0023	1.087584	0.8411
0.1763	1.012925	1.2768	1.010584	1.0139	1.096705	0.8515
0.2073	1.014617	1.2936	1.012131	1.0233	1.114035	0.8747
Diglycine + 3% mannose						
0.0000	1.010238	1.2351	1.008003	0.9875	1.004876	0.7607
0.0320	1.012070	1.2532	1.009770	1.0156	1.006652	0.7721
0.0480	1.012838	1.2626	1.010520	1.0210	1.007396	0.7769
0.0831	1.014930	1.2859	1.012537	1.0326	1.009419	0.7911
0.1120	1.016533	1.3030	1.014080	1.0429	1.010969	0.7965
0.1390	1.018015	1.3175	1.015508	1.0515	1.012403	0.8069
0.1641	1.019380	1.3270	1.016823	1.0625	1.013724	0.8159
0.1980	1.021203	1.3429	1.018581	1.0726	1.015489	0.8272
Diglycine + 5% mannose						
0.0000	1.018880	1.3090	1.016542	1.0111	1.018880	0.8180
0.0567	1.022720	1.3350	1.047914	1.0696	1.049823	0.8276
0.0743	1.023047	1.3407	1.057460	1.0839	1.059282	0.8333
0.1062	1.024798	1.3542	1.074531	1.1088	1.076248	0.8439
0.1323	1.026213	1.3688	1.088279	1.1310	1.089960	0.8521
0.1468	1.026993	1.3750	1.095833	1.1401	1.097512	0.8576
0.1787	1.028693	1.3876	1.011237	1.1663	1.113961	0.8651
0.2148	1.030592	1.4040	1.013452	1.1954	1.132302	0.8763
Diglycine + 1% maltose						
0.0000	1.002800	1.1567	1.000676	0.9075	0.997617	0.7531
0.0623	1.006370	1.1896	1.003156	0.9335	1.001073	0.7736
0.0816	1.007471	1.2033	1.005718	0.9425	1.002139	0.7786
0.1086	1.009007	1.2181	1.006763	0.9503	1.003638	0.7873
0.1303	1.010238	1.2367	1.007433	0.9625	1.004823	0.7964
0.1675	1.012341	1.2527	1.009973	0.9805	1.006865	-0.8072
0.1719	1.012589	1.2586	1.010518	0.9885	1.007107	0.8135
0.2067	1.014546	1.2888	1.012663	1.0018	1.009011	0.8254
Diglycine + 3% maltose						
0.0000	1.010483	1.2278	1.008256	0.9290	1.005079	0.7771
0.0550	1.013546	1.2479	1.011264	0.9473	1.008024	0.7954

Table-2 (contd.)

0.0760	1.014890	1.2613	1.012584	0.9549	1.009372	0.8000
0.0970	1.015848	1.2706	1.013524	0.9647	1.010338	0.8062
0.1150	1.016839	1.2831	1.014496	0.9721	1.011335	0.8134
0.1498	1.018761	1.2974	1.016379	0.9828	1.013229	0.8191
0.1820	1.020551	1.3181	1.018134	0.9984	1.014910	0.8282
0.1917	1.021094	1.3254	1.018665	1.0086	1.015398	0.8351
Diglycine + 5% maltose						
0.0000	1.018011	1.3595	1.015692	1.1670	1.012468	0.8190
0.0576	1.020660	1.3873	1.018373	1.1930	1.015531	0.8313
0.0707	1.022614	1.3986	1.020303	1.2008	1.016232	0.8358
0.0911	1.023609	1.4071	1.021275	1.2108	1.017327	0.8414
0.1238	1.024536	1.4183	1.022178	1.2191	1.019090	0.8499
0.1402	1.026111	1.4281	1.023709	1.2247	1.019977	0.8559
0.1771	1.027950	1.4445	1.025501	1.2356	1.021984	0.8666
0.2045	1.029017	1.4574	1.026546	1.2458	1.023482	0.8757
Diglycine + 1% raffinose						
0.0000	1.002500	1.1711	1.000393	0.9013	0.099733	0.7193
0.0558	1.005718	1.1892	1.003843	0.9252	1.000443	0.7350
0.0796	1.007071	1.2051	1.005223	0.9415	1.001752	0.7465
0.0987	1.008149	1.2181	1.005997	0.9549	1.002795	0.7515
0.1243	1.009584	1.2358	1.007480	0.9683	1.004183	0.7612
0.1478	1.01891	1.2539	1.008190	0.9777	1.005449	0.7664
0.1763	1.012466	1.2768	1.010481	0.9958	1.006973	0.7784
0.2124	1.014445	1.3002	1.010761	1.0132	1.008886	0.7894
Diglycine + 3% raffinose						
0.0000	1.009629	1.2076	1.007437	0.9388	1.004316	0.7581
0.0570	1.012874	1.2393	1.010546	0.9723	1.007451	0.7730
0.0730	1.013795	1.2494	1.011791	0.9752	1.008343	0.7815
0.0881	1.014617	1.2586	1.012994	0.9839	1.009138	0.7858
0.1153	1.016126	1.2756	1.013890	0.9928	1.010600	0.8004
0.1414	1.017561	1.2912	1.015592	1.0061	1.011990	0.8060
0.1885	1.020010	1.3118	1.017386	1.0258	1.014463	0.8188
0.2018	1.020832	1.3231	1.017614	1.0350	1.015153	0.8240
Diglycine + 5% raffinose						
0.0000	1.017167	1.2592	1.014887	1.0227	1.011698	0.8393
0.0571	1.020319	1.2845	1.018011	1.0481	1.014745	0.8604
0.0790	1.021505	1.2981	1.018775	1.0544	1.015893	0.8649
0.0997	1.022623	1.3089	1.020027	1.0612	1.016976	0.8735
0.1214	1.023786	1.3205	1.021039	1.0739	1.018103	0.8779
0.1482	1.025210	1.3296	1.023060	1.0829	1.019485	0.8828
0.1741	1.026573	1.3151	1.024601	1.0934	1.020810	0.8933
0.2081	1.028342	1.3638	1.025587	1.1055	1.022533	0.9032

Table 3. Limiting partial molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0), limiting partial molar adiabatic compressibilities ($K_{\phi,s}^0$) and experimental slopes (S_V and S_K) of diglycine in aqueous saccharides at various temperatures

T (K)	$V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$S_V \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{L}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)	$K_{\phi,s}^0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{GPa}^{-1}$)	$S_K \times 10^6$ ($\text{kg m}^3 \text{mol}^{-2} \text{GPa}^{-1}$)
Diglycine + 1% mannose				
288.15	73.82 (± 0.01)	5.28 (± 0.06)	-43.03 (± 2.24)	2.84 (± 2.00)
298.15	74.85 (± 0.02)	5.94 (± 0.12)	-38.71 (± 1.10)	0.49 (± 0.81)
308.15	75.75 (± 0.03)	6.03 (± 0.21)	-34.55 (± 0.91)	3.98 (± 0.66)
Diglycine + 3% mannose				
288.15	74.68 (± 0.03)	5.06 (± 0.23)	-39.57 (± 2.02)	3.53 (± 1.04)
298.15	75.59 (± 0.29)	5.66 (± 0.21)	-34.20 (± 1.36)	4.22 (± 0.58)
308.15	76.56 (± 0.04)	5.10 (± 0.03)	-29.54 (± 0.86)	6.70 (± 4.80)
Diglycine + 5% mannose				
288.15	74.84 (± 0.02)	6.61 (± 0.11)	-47.65 (± 1.65)	34.03 (± 10.63)
298.15	75.99 (± 0.01)	6.27 (± 0.12)	-33.73 (± 1.89)	14.11 (± 12.17)
308.15	76.68 (± 0.03)	6.19 (± 0.18)	-27.36 (± 3.30)	-22.64 (± 21.29)
Diglycine + 1% maltose				
288.15	74.61 (± 0.01)	-1.89 (± 0.13)	-48.84 (± 2.45)	9.58 (± 1.12)
298.15	75.74 (± 0.01)	-1.88 (± 0.09)	-39.24 (± 1.28)	7.42 (± 0.90)
308.15	76.58 (± 0.09)	-1.93 (± 0.07)	-34.46 (± 0.90)	4.06 (± 0.34)
Diglycine + 3% maltose				
288.15	76.44 (± 0.03)	-3.22 (± 0.25)	-44.95 (± 1.90)	3.32 (± 0.89)
298.15	77.42 (± 0.02)	-2.69 (± 0.17)	-38.25 (± 0.82)	2.66 (± 0.62)
308.15	77.90 (± 0.02)	-2.86 (± 0.16)	-33.89 (± 0.90)	2.05 (± 0.67)
Diglycine + 5% maltose				
288.15	77.23 (± 0.01)	-9.26 (± 0.08)	-43.87 (± 2.01)	-4.92 (± 1.48)
298.15	78.30 (± 0.15)	-8.83 (± 0.11)	-39.70 (± 3.30)	19.8 (± 2.43)
308.15	78.86 (± 0.10)	-8.60 (± 0.07)	-33.17 (± 1.22)	1.22 (± 0.90)
Diglycine + 1% raffinose				
288.15	73.90 (± 0.02)	5.10 (± 0.21)	-50.33 (± 4.09)	19.09 (± 1.12)
298.15	75.09 (± 0.02)	4.87 (± 0.15)	-41.94 (± 1.76)	11.88 (± 0.90)
308.15	75.99 (± 0.01)	4.48 (± 0.10)	-36.70 (± 0.90)	10.38 (± 0.34)
Diglycine + 3% raffinose				
288.15	74.47 (± 0.02)	5.36 (± 0.16)	-44.85 (± 1.90)	6.02 (± 0.89)
298.15	75.65 (± 0.11)	4.88 (± 0.08)	-38.27 (± 0.82)	5.43 (± 0.62)
308.15	76.50 (± 0.01)	4.60 (± 0.06)	-33.73 (± 0.90)	5.23 (± 0.67)
Diglycine + 5% raffinose				
288.15	76.08 (± 0.01)	4.96 (± 0.13)	-46.22 (± 3.32)	20.03 (± 0.66)
298.15	77.21 (± 0.02)	4.33 (± 0.19)	-38.87 (± 2.37)	17.66 (± 0.17)
308.15	78.06 (± 0.02)	3.89 (± 0.15)	-31.95 (± 0.90)	5.15 (± 0.24)

Foot note : V_{ϕ}^0 for diglycine in water : $74.14 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 288.15 K, $75.24 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K and $76.21 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 308.15 K and $K_{\phi,s}^0$ for diglycine in water : $-53.22 (\pm 0.195) \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{GPa}^{-1}$ at 288.15 K, $-42.30 (\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{GPa}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K and $-33.06 (\pm 0.09) \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{GPa}^{-1}$ at 308.15 K are experimental measurements of density and speed of sound of diglycine in water.

from water to aqueous saccharide solutions have been calculated by the equation,

$$\Delta Y_{\phi}^0 = Y_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in aqueous saccharide solution)} - Y_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (5)$$

where Y_{ϕ}^0 denotes V_{ϕ}^0 or $K_{\phi,s}^0$ and are listed in Table 3. The calculated results are given in Table 4 and are illus-

trated in Figs. 2 and 3 and Table 4 shows that the $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values increase with the concentration of mannose except at 288.15 K. The effect is more pronounced at lower concentration than at higher concentration of mannose. Further, the $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values increase at lower mass% and then decrease at higher mass% of maltose or raffinose at 288.15 and 298.15 K but the behavior is opposite where the values of $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ are decreased at lower concentration of raffinose. The more positive ΔV_{ϕ}^0 and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values

Table 4. Transfer volumes (ΔV_{ϕ}^0), limiting partial molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) and transfer adiabatic compressibilities ($\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$) of diglycine in aqueous saccharides at various temperatures

<i>T</i> (K)	$\Delta V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)	ϕ_E^0 (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Diglycine + 1% mannose			
288.15	-0.32	10.19	0.110
298.15	-0.39	3.59	0.097
308.15	-0.46	-1.49	0.084
Diglycine + 3% mannose			
288.15	0.54	13.65	0.088
298.15	0.36	8.10	0.094
308.15	0.35	3.52	0.100
Diglycine + 5% mannose			
288.15	0.70	5.57	0.138
298.15	0.76	8.57	0.092
308.15	0.47	5.70	0.046
Diglycine + 1% maltose			
288.15	0.47	4.38	0.127
298.15	0.31	3.06	0.098
308.15	0.37	-1.40	0.069
Diglycine + 3% maltose			
288.15	2.30	8.27	0.123
298.15	2.19	4.05	0.072
308.15	1.69	-0.83	0.023
Diglycine + 5% maltose			
288.15	3.09	9.35	0.072
298.15	3.07	2.60	0.061
308.15	2.65	0.11	0.050
Diglycine + 1% raffinose			
288.15	-0.24	-2.89	0.133
298.15	-0.14	-0.36	0.104
308.15	-0.22	3.64	0.075
Diglycine + 3% raffinose			
288.15	0.33	8.37	0.135
298.15	0.41	4.03	0.102
308.15	0.29	-0.67	0.067
Diglycine + 5% raffinose			
288.15	1.94	7.00	0.127
298.15	1.98	3.43	0.099
308.15	1.85	1.11	0.071

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} against molal concentration m for diglycine in 1 mass% of mannose at 288.15 K (■), 298.15 K (●) and 308.15 K (▲). Solid lines are obtained from eq. (4) and symbols are experimental data.

Fig. 2. Plots of transfer volumes ΔV_{ϕ}^0 against mass% of raffinose for diglycine at 288.15 K (■), 298.15 K (●) and 308.15 K (▲).

Fig. 3. Plots of transfer adiabatic compressibilities $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ against mass% of maltose for diglycine at 288.15 K (■), 298.15 K (●) and 308.15 K (▲)

in case of all the saccharides at higher concentrations with diglycine indicate the dominance of charged end groups, NH_3^+ and COO^- , while negative ΔV_{ϕ}^0 and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values at lower concentrations indicate the effect of hydrophobic parts that is, the interactions between the -OH group of saccharides and zwitterionic centre of diglycine increase with increasing saccharide concentrations. For diglycine in aqueous mannose or raffinose solutions, the interaction between the -OH group of mannose or raffinose and non-polar group of diglycine are predominant. The overall effect is that the charged end groups of diglycine influences electrostatically surrounding water molecules, so called electrostriction. In the other words, the hydration co-spheres of NH_3^+ COO^- , which are more hydrated than that of mannose or raffinose, will be effected to a greater extent than the later, resulting in higher values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 . In case of maltose as compared to mannose or raffinose, electrostriction decreases at higher concentration of maltose. In the 5 mass% of maltose, the magnitude of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 is higher. It appears that at high percentage of maltose, diglycine might be behaving as a weak structure-breaker. In the lower concentration of mannose and raffinose, the interaction of water with mannose or raffinose is not so strong and does not involve any structural changes. It appears that at small mass% (1 mass% of mannose and of raffinose), diglycine might be behaving as a net structure-breaker due to the interactions be-

tween -OH group of mannose or raffinose with the zwitterionic center of diglycine. The structure breaking effects of diglycine decreases due to its interaction with mannose or raffinose molecules.

We have also explained the ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values on the basis of the co-sphere overlap model^{31,32} in terms of solute-solute interactions. According to this model, hydrophilic-ionic group interactions contribute positively, whereas hydrophilic-hydrophobic group interactions contribute negatively to the ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values. For diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions, the former types of interactions are predominant over the latter. With the increase of the saccharide concentrations, the interactions between the -OH group of the saccharide and the zwitterionic center of the diglycine also increase gradually which are not compensated by the interactions between the -OH group of the saccharide and non-polar group of the diglycine. It may be noted that ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values of maltose raffinose are higher than those of diglycine in mannose and raffinose at higher mass%. As a result greater electrostriction of solvent water is produced as in case of diglycine in mannose and raffinose, leading to less values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 . In other order, the interaction between the -OH group of mannose or raffinose and the non-polar (-CH₃) group of diglycine leads to a larger decrease in the ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values as a results of their cosphere overlap. Also, this leads to an increase in the structure-breaking tendency if diglycine in mannose or raffinose.

The variation of limiting partial molar volume ΔV_{ϕ}^0 with temperature can be expressed

$$\Delta V_{\phi}^0 = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (6)$$

where T is the temperature in degrees Kelvin and a , b and c are constants.

The partial molar expansibilities at infinite dilution ϕ_E^0 were obtained by differentiating eq. (6) with respect to temperature,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T)_p = b + 2cT \quad (7)$$

The ϕ_E^0 values of the diglycine at different temperatures are determined and included in Table 4. It may be noted that ϕ_E^0 values of diglycine decrease with rise in temperature except with 3 mass% of mannose, indicating that diglycine acts as strong structure-breaker in higher mass% of saccharides. This indicates maximum structure-breaking of saccharides on addition of diglycine in

the higher concentration region of saccharide. At the concentration of saccharides and at all the temperatures, the ϕ_E^0 values are positive, means favoring the solute-solute interactions. The effect is that electrostricted water may be released from the loose solvation layers of diglycine at higher temperature. This is reflected in higher V_ϕ^0 values. Further, the effect is removal of water molecules favor diglycine-saccharides or diglycine-diglycine interactions, indicating the structure-breaking effect of diglycine in higher concentration region of saccharides and at higher temperatures.

The $K_{\phi,s}^0$ values are negative and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values are positive for diglycine at higher concentration range of all saccharides. This observation again supports the positive ΔV_ϕ^0 and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ results that the dehydration of solute and co-solute occurs more in diglycine and it is increased with the increase of concentration of saccharides.

The partial molar volume of the amino acids can be examined by a simple model³³,

$$V_\phi^0(\text{amino acid}) = V_\phi^0(\text{int}) + V_\phi^0(\text{elect}) \quad (8)$$

where $V_\phi^0(\text{elect})$ is the electrostriction partial molar volume due to the hydration of the amino acid and can be estimated from experimentally measured values of $V_\phi^0(\text{amino acid})$, and $V_\phi^0(\text{int})$ is the intrinsic partial molar volume of the amino acid and has been calculated from the following expressions³³,

$$V_\phi^0(\text{int}) = (0.7/0.6) V_\phi^0(\text{cryst}) \quad (9)$$

and

$$V_\phi^0(\text{int}) = (0.7/0.634) V_\phi^0(\text{cryst}) \quad (10)$$

where $V_\phi^0(\text{cryst}) (= \text{mol. wt.}/d_{\text{cryst}})$ is the crystal molar volume, 0.7 is the packing density for molecules in organic crystals and 0.634 is the packing density for random packing spheres. The values of $V_\phi^0(\text{int})$ for the amino acids have been estimated from eqs. (9) and (10) using d_{cryst} values for diglycine (1.534 g cm^{-3}) taken from literature³⁴.

The change in volume due to electrostriction can be related to the number of water molecules n_H hydrated to the amino acid by^{35,36},

$$n_H = V_\phi^0(\text{elect})/(V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0) \quad (11)$$

where $V_{\phi,e}^0$ is the molar volume of electrostricted water and $V_{\phi,b}^0$ is the molar volume of bulk water ($18.069 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K). The reported value³³ of

$(V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0)$ is $\approx -3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K. Using the value of $(V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0)$ and the values of $V_\phi^0(\text{elect})$ (calculated from both the methods), the n_H values were estimated from eq. (11) and are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Hydration number (n_H) of diglycine in aqueous solutions of saccharides at 298.15 K

m_B (mol kg ⁻¹)	n_H		
	From volume		From compressibility
	Using eq. (9)	Using eq. (10)	Using eq. (12)
	Diglycine in water		
0.0000	7.64	6.01	5.22
	Diglycine in aqueous mannose		
0.0560	7.76	6.13	4.70
0.1716	7.54	5.90	4.22
0.2921	7.42	5.78	4.16
	Diglycine in aqueous maltose		
0.0280	7.49	5.86	4.84
0.0858	6.98	5.35	4.72
0.1460	6.72	5.08	4.90
	Diglycine in aqueous raffinose		
0.0169	7.69	6.06	5.17
0.0520	7.52	5.89	4.76
0.0885	7.05	5.41	4.79

Further, the number of water molecules n_H hydrated to the amino acids were calculated by using the method given by Millero *et al.*^{33,37},

$$n_H = -K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect})/V_{\phi,b}^0 K_{s,b}^0 \quad (12)$$

where $K_{s,b}^0$ is the isothermal compressibility of bulk water. The value of $V_{\phi,b}^0 K_{s,b}^0$ is $\approx 0.81 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ GPa}^{-1}$. The electrostriction partial molar compressibility $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect})$ can be calculated from the experimentally measured values of $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid})$ from,

$$K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect}) = K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid}) - K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \quad (13)$$

where $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int})$ ³⁸ = $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{isomer})$ for diglycine. Since one would expect $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int})$ to be small and it is less than $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ for ionic crystals and many organic solutes in water³³. So, one can assume $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \approx 0$. Therefore, for $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \approx 0$, eq. (13) becomes,

$$K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect}) = K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid}) \quad (14)$$

The values of n_H calculated from eqs. (12) and (14) are listed in Table 5. The values of n_H (in water) calculated

by these methods, from volume and compressibility data are also shown in Table 5. These values decrease with the increase in the concentration of maltose except with raffinose or mannose at lower mass%, which again indicates the increase in solute-cosolute interaction with the increase in saccharide concentration. Furthermore, the values of n_H for diglycine at lower concentration of mannose or raffinose are higher than in water and reverse is the case with maltose. Thus the hydrophilic-hydrophobic group interactions are higher and as a result, greater electrostriction of solvent water is produced, leading to higher values of n_H at lower concentration and smaller values of ΔV_ϕ^0 as compared to diglycine with maltose.

Viscosities and densities of diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions with the molal concentration at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K are given in Table 2. It is evident from the Table 2 that the values of viscosities for diglycine in different aqueous mixtures of saccharides at three temperatures increase with the increase in concentration of each saccharides.

In general, the variation of relative viscosity η_r for diglycine in aqueous saccharides solution have been represented by Jones-Dole³⁹ equation :

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad (15)$$

The values of B -coefficients are calculated by the method of least square fitting the experimental data in eq. (15) and these values are given in Table 6 along with standard errors. Fig. 4 shows a plot of η/η_0 against C for diglycine in different mass% of saccharides at 288.15 K.

Table 6. Values of B -coefficients of Jones-Dole equation for diglycine in aqueous solutions of saccharides

Mass% (Sacc- haride)	$B \times 10^3$		
	288.15 K	298.15 K	308.15 K
Diglycine + aqueous mannose ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)			
1.0	1.9619 (± 0.0473)	2.0693 (± 0.0495)	1.0463 (± 0.0293)
3.0	2.2264 (± 0.0404)	2.1175 (± 0.1155)	2.3064 (± 0.0246)
5.0	2.3064 (± 0.0246)	2.1917 (± 0.0198)	3.4772 (± 0.0896)
Diglycine + aqueous maltose			
1.0	1.9513 (± 0.0403)	2.0442 (± 0.0403)	2.2414 (± 0.0389)
3.0	2.6027 (± 0.0674)	2.4734 (± 0.0674)	2.6794 (± 0.0496)
5.0	2.8963 (± 0.0571)	2.9145 (± 0.0930)	3.1441 (± 0.0729)
Diglycine + aqueous raffinose			
1.0	2.0820 (± 0.0976)	1.7171 (± 0.0976)	2.1526 (± 0.0526)
3.0	2.1679 (± 0.0206)	2.0097 (± 0.0379)	2.3185 (± 0.0491)
5.0	2.7562 (± 0.1858)	2.6006 (± 0.0282)	2.7204 (± 0.0587)

Fig. 4. Plots η/η_0 against C for diglycine in 1 mass% mannose (■), 3 mass% mannose (●), 5 mass% mannose (▲) at 288.15 K.

Table 6 shows that the values of B -coefficients for diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions are positive in all the concentration range at the measured temperatures, showing the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions. So, diglycine behaves as structure-maker. It is also clear from Table 6 that the values of B -coefficients are higher at higher mass% of all saccharides at all temperatures, suggesting that ion-solvent interactions are strong in these concentration range and at higher temperatures. In other words, ion-solvation increases with the increase in the mass% of saccharides and at all temperatures or it may be said that for all these saccharides have more affinity for water than the added solute diglycine. Moreover, the B -coefficient values are very high in aqueous maltose solutions suggesting that diglycine behaves as weak structure-breaker at higher concentration range of maltose. Further, a perusal of Table 6 shows that the B -values of diglycine increase with increase in temperature in case of maltose. These are very prominent at higher mass% of maltose. So its derivative of temperature⁴⁰ (dB/dT) is positive. Diglycine can be classified as a structure-breaker at higher mass% of maltose since the sign of dB/dT values gives important informations regarding the structure-making and structure-breaking role of the solute in the solvent media^{41,42} rather than simply the B -coefficient. Therefore, the charged end group of diglycine is involved in hydrogen bonding with the solvent components resulting

in the breaking of the solvent structure. This also supports the conclusion drawn from ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values.

The viscosity data for the solutions of diglycine in different mixtures of saccharides at the three temperatures have also been analyzed on the basis of transition state theory, as suggested by Feakins *et al.*⁴³. According to this theory, the *B*-parameter is given by the equation :

$$B = (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)/1000 + \bar{V}_1/1000 \quad (16)$$

$$[(\Delta\mu_2^{0*} - \Delta\mu_1^{0*})/RT]$$

where V_1^0 ($= \sum x_i M_i/\rho$ is the mean volume of the solvent) and V_2^0 ($= V_{\phi}^0$) is the partial molar volume at infinite dilution of the solute. The terms x_i and M represent the mole fractions and molar masses of water (1) and saccharide (2), and ρ is the density of solvent mixture (saccharide + water). The free energy of activation per mole of the solvent $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ and the free energy of activation per mole of the solute $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ were calculated⁴⁴ by using the equations,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0*} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0/h N) \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0*} = \Delta\mu_1^{0*} + RT/\bar{V}_1^0 [1000 B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (18)$$

where *h* is Planck's constant, *N* is Avogadro number, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent and the other symbols have their usual meanings. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$, $\bar{V}_1^0$ and $\bar{V}_2^0$ calculated at the three temperatures are given in Table 7.

Table 7. Values of $\bar{V}_1^0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), $\bar{V}_2^0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) and $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) of diglycine in aqueous solutions of saccharide at various temperatures

Mass % (Saccharides)		288.15 K	298.15 K	308.15 K
Diglycine + mannose				
1.0	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.12	18.16	18.22
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	73.82	74.85	75.75
	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.06	26.40	26.64
3.0	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	292.80	316.59	343.05
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.31	18.35	18.41
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	74.68	75.59	76.56
5.0	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.23	26.58	26.80
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	324.90	320.36	355.84
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.47	18.52	18.57
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	74.84	75.99	76.68
5.0	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	2.37	26.66	27.01
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	322.83	343.05	514.74
	Diglycine + maltose			
1.0	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.31	18.35	18.41

Table-7 (contd.)

3.0	$\bar{V}_2^0$	74.68	75.74	76.58
	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.06	26.36	26.78
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	262.67	310.26	346.78
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.33	18.38	18.43
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	76.44	77.42	77.90
	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.21	26.43	26.86
5.0	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	347.76	367.96	407.59
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.57	18.61	18.67
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	77.23	78.30	78.86
5.0	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.50	27.02	27.03
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	381.22	423.18	466.72
	Diglycine + raffinose			
1.0	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.14	18.18	18.24
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	73.90	75.09	75.99
	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.06	26.33	26.64
3.0	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	308.47	268.21	337.10
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.35	18.39	18.45
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	74.47	75.64	76.50
5.0	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.17	26.46	26.80
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	316.78	305.07	356.81
	$\bar{V}_1^0$	18.75	18.81	18.86
	$\bar{V}_2^0$	76.08	77.21	78.06
5.0	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	26.32	26.73	27.11
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	385.95	377.13	404.68

It is evident from Table 7, $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ does not change appreciably with the change in the concentration of saccharides in water and also with the increase in temperature. It is also clear from Table 7 that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ change with the mass% of saccharides and with temperature for diglycine. Again, it also shows that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ are positive and larger than $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ indicating a stronger ion-solvent interaction. In other words, the formation of the transition state is less favoured in the presence of diglycine. This means that the formation of transition state is accompanied by the breaking and distortion of the intermolecular forces in solvent structure.

Experimental

The amino acid used in this study, diglycine was analytical grade reagent obtained from Hi Media, Mumbai. The material was used after drying over silica gel in a vacuum desiccator at room temperature for a minimum of 48 h. The saccharides i.e. mannose (Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai), maltose and raffinose (S.D.Fine-chem., Mumbai) were dried under vacuum at 50 °C and kept

over P₂O₅ in vacuum desiccator for a minimum of 48 h before use. Water used in this experiment was deionized, distilled, and degassed. Solutions of saccharide were prepared by mass in the range 1–5% and used on the day they were prepared. Solutions of diglycine in concentrations range of 0.05–0.20 mol kg⁻¹ were made by mass on the molality concentration scale with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ on an Afcoset electronic balance (India, Model ER-182A). Uncertainties in solution concentration were estimated at $\pm 2 \times 10^{-4}$ mol kg⁻¹ in calculations. Densities (ρ) and speeds of sound (u) of amino acid in different aqueous saccharides and at different temperatures were measured simultaneously, using an Anton Paar DSA 5000 instrument. Both the sound and density are extremely sensitive to temperature, so it is controlled to $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K by built-in solid state thermostat. Before each series of measurements, the instrument was calibrated at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K with the doubly distilled and degassed water and dry air. There was a good agreement between experimental and literature values as for water at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K giving values 0.999100, 0.997048 and 0.994032 g cm⁻³ for density⁴⁵ and 1466.32, 1496.76 and 1519.78 m s⁻¹ for ultrasonic speed⁴⁶ respectively. The reproducibility of density and speed of sound measurements was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ kg m⁻³ and $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ m s⁻¹, respectively and the uncertainties of these were assumed to be less than 5×10^{-3} kg m⁻³ and 5×10^{-2} m s⁻¹ of densities and speeds of sound of water at the required temperatures.

Viscosity was measured by means of a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer with a flow time of about 330 s for distilled water at 298.15 K. The flow time was measured with a stop watch capable of registering time accurate to ± 0.1 s. An average of three or four sets of flow times for each fluid was taken for the purpose of the calculation of viscosity. The viscometer was calibrated at the working temperatures before use. The calibration of viscometer was first done with triply distilled water and double distilled benzene. Care was taken to prevent evaporation during measurements. The viscosity values are reproducible to within $\pm 0.0005 \times 10^{-3}$ mPas. All the measurements were carried out in a thermostatically controlled well-stirred water-bath with temperature controlled to ± 0.01 K.

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